

This document forms section eight of the University of Bath's Responsible Research Assessment Guidance and should be read alongside [the full guidance](#). You can find more information on the [RRA webpage](#).

8. A framework for writing and assessing statements

Key points covered in this section:

- Combine context and evidence in statements to show what was achieved and why it matters,
- Focus on individual contribution and significance, not just outputs or metrics.
- Use a consistent framework, such as the CARE model to help with assessment.

Candidate or applicant statements are often used in assessments. Whether via CVs, grant applications or interviews – individuals put forward examples of their contributions, describe the quality of their work, and explain its impact to make their case.

Statements can be particularly useful when the reviewers are not experts in the field, or do not have time to read the outputs themselves. They also help provide context for supporting data and evidence.

However, it is important to remember that context without evidence (whether qualitative or quantitative) could be just as meaningless as evidence without context. Statements can also be subject to bias. If not handled carefully, they could, for example, disadvantage colleagues with dyslexia, or those for whom English is a second language.

When reviewing written statements, assessors should focus on the content, not the tone or choice of words.

Think of statements as important mechanisms to contextualise evidence.

The CARE model (Context, Action, Result, Evidence) below provides a consistent way of supporting individuals and assessors to understand how they can present, and consistently assess, written statements for robustness.

Figure 2: The CARE model

Below are three examples of candidate statements. Only one applies the CARE model correctly.

Example 1: My work explores innovative approaches to reimagining patient triage, drawing on diverse and emerging data sources to inform the development of forward-thinking predictive models. It reflects a strong commitment to inclusive research practices, particularly in embedding meaningful public and patient involvement and engagement (PPIE).

The approach has gained traction within the field, contributing to wider conversations around data-driven healthcare and equitable access. It has been recognised through high citation rates, inclusion in policy discussions, and has attracted attention in other domains. Media coverage has further amplified its reach, leading to new opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange. Overall, the work is helping to shape future directions in health informatics and patient-centred care.

Example 2: I am first author on a paper “Incorporating Socioeconomic and environmental data into patient triage”, which was published in *The Lancet Digital Health (JIFX)*. The paper has attracted 300 citations from 10 countries with 200k views and two collaboration requests.

Example 3: In health informatics, I observed that existing patient triage algorithms often overlooked social determinants of health, which significantly affect outcomes.

To address this, I led a study with BANES Trust integrating socioeconomic and environmental data into a predictive triage model. This was the first time local authority, patient, and longitudinal research data were combined in this way. I was responsible for funding attraction, model design, analysis, and led the write-up as first author.

A resulting paper was published in *The Lancet Digital Health*, achieving a Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) of 3.2—over three times the global average—demonstrating strong influence. It was cited as a ‘best-practice’ approach in a Department for Health Review and, following a BBC feature with 200,000 views, led to collaboration requests from two additional trusts to pilot the model.

Assessing the examples:

Example 1 demonstrates how statements that provide context without any evidence are difficult to assess robustly and often our gauge of them will depend on the writing style rather than the content.

Example 2 provides evidence without any context of what the individual did, why the work was significant, or the context in which it was carried out.

Example 3 combined evidence and context effectively so we have a clearer picture of the individual's contribution, the work's quality and its significance.

For more information read [the full guidance](#) or visit the [RRA webpage](#).